

CERTAINTY TUC's DMP

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for EC-Earth model output produced at the Technical University of Crete (TUC) is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for TUC is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

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Grant

CERTAINTY

Researchers

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Organizations

TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF CRETE, Finnish Meteorological
Institute

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: CERTAINTY TUC's DMP

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Organizations:

TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF CRETE

Finnish Meteorological Institute

Contact: Apostolos Voulgarakis

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission|EC

Grants: CERTAINTY

Project: CERTAINTY

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

EC-Earth model output

The Earth system model EC-Earth provides output of simulated physical and chemical variables from different components of the Earth system. Within CERTAINTY, the data will be used to analyse aerosol forcings and interactions between aerosols, clouds, and climate.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Secondary data derived from raw EC-Earth output.

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Publications describing EC-Earth3-AerChem and related EC-Earth3 configurations:

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-5637-2021>

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-2973-2022>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

Project partners, climate research community.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We will produce descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

zenodo.org

Zenodo is an open-access generic repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It enables researchers to share and preserve any research outputs in any size, format, and from all fields of science. Zenodo supports the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles and offers features like DOI (Digital Object Identifier) assignment for easy citation of research materials. This platform also integrates with GitHub, allowing researchers to archive software, and

offers the capability to upload datasets, publications, research software, reports, and other research-related materials.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

EC-Earth model output

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo time. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license. After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

TUC aims to retain model output data for a period of some years. Should external users continue to utilize the data extensively, this retention period may be prolonged.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

EC-Earth has been validated against in-situ observations, ground and satellite-based remote sensing. Data conforms the Climate Model Output Rewriter (CMOR) standards (see <https://cmor.llnl.gov/>).

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management.

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